

Distributed MIMO Systems for 6G

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Abstract—This study focuses on Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) systems and provides a discussion about their role in next generation networks. The paradigm shift to distributed networks offers great potential to address the 6G requirements, through macro diversity. As 6G scenarios and use cases continue to emerge, new challenges are likely to arise that may affect the widespread implementation of D-MIMO. To address those, different deployment options have been proposed for roll-out considerations. They are composed of several sub-components that can be categorized as (i) wireless or wired fronthaul/backhaul, (ii) analog or digital signals, (iii) distributed or centralized processing, and (iv) coherent or non-coherent transmission. To facilitate standardization efforts, we provide 3GPP-aligned terminology for network nodes, multi-point transmission and reception schemes. In order to enable large-scale implementation of D-MIMO systems, it is important to determine the needed amount of distribution, develop practical solutions for high-frequency bands, and ways to convey data that meet the transport requirements. On this regard, we discuss key enablers and present simulation results for D-MIMO systems towards 6G. In particular, we present solutions for D-MIMO networks in dynamic scenarios related to channel estimation and layer-1 mobility considering coherent and non-coherent joint transmission, and analog fronthaul implementation using analog-radio-over-fiber that are promising for high (upper mm-Wave and (sub-)THz) carrier frequencies, as well as integrated access and backhaul, network-controlled repeaters, and reconfigurable intelligent surfaces that are possible enablers for cost-efficient network densification at both low (cm-Wave, lower mm-Wave) and high carrier frequencies.

Index Terms—6G, Distributed MIMO, D-MIMO, cell-free massive MIMO, 5G, network controlled repeaters, NCR, integrated access and backhaul, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, RIS, L1 mobility, non-coherent transmission, channel estimation, IAB, analog fronthaul.

I. INTRODUCTION

6G technology will need to bring significant advancements such as high radio performance in terms of both ultra-high data rate links and capacity. While optimizing traffic capacity is important, energy efficiency, transport efficiency, robustness, latency, mobility, security, deployment flexibility, and footprint are crucial for 6G network planning and deployment. Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) networks can improve these metrics by offering a high level of macro-diversity

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and consistent service quality across the coverage area, by coordinating distributed Radio Units (RUs) [1]. 6G should support scalable D-MIMO networks for a range of frequencies and take deployment options into account. Such systems allow for multi-user MIMO with Coherent Joint Transmission (C-JT) and interference suppression capabilities and can provide robust links that can handle a high amount of traffic, regardless of the site location. Considering the scenario requirements, it should also integrate with legacy systems and reuse existing deployments for efficient use of resources. There are various research in the literature covering channel estimation [1]–[4], flexible RU selection/clustering [2], [5], [6], precoding [7], [8], resource allocation [9], and power control [10] problems.

The main challenge for the widespread implementation of D-MIMO is the cost of installing many nodes in different locations that require high-speed Fronthaul (FH) connections. These installations need to be easy to deploy, have a small visual impact and be flexible to scale and expand [11]. D-MIMO networks can be deployed in areas where capacity cannot be met by macro sites in an efficient way and used to improve performance in high-density urban areas such as public squares, stadiums, and airports. For indoor deployment scenarios, such as factories, warehouses, and offices, this technique can be used to enhance reliability and resilience aspects. It can provide reliable and resilient mobility without frequent handovers. In some scenarios, coverage from existing macro deployments may not exist. In such cases, in addition to provide data boosting, D-MIMO network also needs to provide coverage for standalone operation.

D-MIMO will be able to address 6G challenges at both low (cm-Wave, lower mm-Wave) and high (upper mm-Wave and (sub-)THz) carrier frequencies. It has the potential to allow for further densification, increasing consistent area capacity, and mitigating unreliable links due to shadowing or blockage, benefiting from the macro-diversity. In addition, it allows sufficient link margin despite output power limitations and high path-loss at upper mm-Wave and (sub-)THz frequencies and allows for lowering effective isotropic radiated power, hence simplifying deployment [12]. Moreover, D-MIMO with multi-node connectivity will allow contiguous coverage under mobility.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, User Equipments (UEs) can be served by several transmission nodes that are controlled by one or several Distributed Units (DUs) via fiber-optic or

Fig. 1. Illustration of D-MIMO network with layer-1 mobility

wireless FH links. Wireless FH links can be implemented using dedicated frequency bands or using the same bands as for access, so-called Integrated Access Backhaul/Fronthaul (IAB). Along with D-MIMO networks, different approaches have been proposed for robust coverage and network performance, e.g., Network Controlled Repeaters (NCRs) [13] and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) that can be deployed with D-MIMO networks to assist the communications. In this paper, D-MIMO networks and all these network extensions are regarded as a distributed MIMO system allowing transmission nodes closer to the UEs, as such, D-MIMO systems can implement various levels of cooperative MIMO systems ranging from Distributed Antenna Systems (DAS) to Joint Transmission Coordinated Multi-Point (JT-CoMP) incorporating repeater and reconfigurable surface capabilities.

Given this broad perspective, various terminologies have been employed. As the network nodes, one may see Access Point (AP), Antenna Processing Unit (APU), Central Processing Unit (CPU), RU, DU, Central Unit (CU), and Transmission Reception Point (TRP) in the literature and discussions. 3GPP has defined CoMP schemes in LTE and New Radio (NR) [14]: (i) Non-coherent JT (NC-JT Case 1), where different layers are transmitted across TRPs, (ii) NC-JT Case 2a, where different layers are transmitted across TRPs with spatial diversity/multiplexing, e.g., space-time block codes, (iii) NC Single Frequency Network (SFN) JT (NC-JT Case 2b) where the same layer is transmitted across TRPs, (iv) C-JT. It is likely that multi-TRP will converge to D-MIMO with each new release. 3GPP uses TRP terminology which, however, does not include radio split dimension, thus, we will use RU and DU throughout the paper. NCR has also been recently considered as one study-item in 3GPP Rel-18 [15], and the discussions are continuing in a work item.

II. RADIO ARCHITECTURE

Different scenarios and requirements affect the deployment of D-MIMO networks. At sub-6 GHz, D-MIMO is mainly driven by the need for high-spectral efficiency, whereas at very high frequencies, the need for macro-diversity is due to less reliable radio channels. Distributed systems allow for an architecture where serving antennas are closer to UEs, thus can provide more reliable links. Higher frequencies and larger bandwidth in the access put higher demands on the

FH/BH for the distributed antennas and the processing of the high bandwidth signals. D-MIMO sub-components can be categorized in the following ways:

- *Transport media*: The FH/BH can be wired or wireless.
- *Signaling*: The data transmitted over the transport media can further be distinguished by being digitally encoded (e.g., CPRI), or an analog signal modulated onto a carrier.
- *Processing*: Processing, e.g., beamforming, in different nodes can either be performed analog or digitally. A further distinction can be made between centralized and distributed processing.
- *Transmission*: Joint transmission schemes can either be based on coherent or non-coherent operation.

To make D-MIMO networks work on a large scale, we need to figure out how much distribution is needed and develop practical solutions for high-frequency bands, and ways to convey data that meet the transport requirements. The ideal solution would be phase C-JT and centralized processing, which would be hard to realize and meet the necessary requirements. The other option would be phase NC-JT, but it would be inefficient due to the lack of interference cancellation. Hence, there is a need to find the right balance.

Sub-THz frequencies allow for high bandwidth and throughput, but digital processing in these bands can be power-intensive and increase the cost and size of the processing unit. To mitigate these issues, digital processing can be moved from the RU to the DU, requiring high-capacity analog FH connections. On the other hand, using lower frequencies with limited bandwidth allows for local digital processing at the RU. This approach, distributed processing, reduces the amount of information exchanged between the RU and DU. The choice between distributed and centralized processing poses new constraints for the FH in D-MIMO networks.

Furthermore, there are many challenges with FH, some of which were identified in 5G and others that are new for 6G, which include increased system bandwidth, support for multiple frequency bands and antennas, resource pooling, joint processing, interference coordination, etc. Lower layer split options need to balance RU and FH complexity, cost, and capacity while maintaining high performance for various topologies, e.g., star and cascaded models. These challenges center around how to handle functionalities such as where channel estimation is performed, where beamforming weights are calculated, and which data to transport over the FH interface and their requirements. It is generally best to connect RUs with cables if it is simple to run a single cable through multiple RUs. However, wireless links can also be used for FH which provides additional flexibility in deployment. Higher frequencies, e.g., sub-THz having a lot of available spectrum and not much traffic in the early stages of utilization, can be used for FH. Since RUs are typically not mobile, it is easy to maintain robust FH links. Random blockages caused by moving objects can be handled by using redundant links.

Due to similar reasons, IAB techniques, where a portion of radio resources are utilized for wireless FH/BH, have recently gained significant attention. IAB offers a flexible

wireless BH solution using the latest 3GPP NR technology in the International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT) frequency bands, but also offers existing cellular services from the same node. This makes IAB a complementary option to microwave point-to-point backhauling in densely populated urban and suburban areas, albeit at the cost of using IMT bands for both access and BH traffic. The design of IAB architecture is built on the concept of separating the CU and the DU in the gNB. The IAB donor, which includes both the CU and DU functions, is connected to the core network through conventional non-IAB backhauling methods such as fiber optics [16], [17]. Similar approach can be applied on the FH such that IAB donor can include both RU and DU functions.

Fig. 2. Illustration of architectural options and technology sub-components for D-MIMO.

A. Analog approaches

1) *Network-controlled Repeaters and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces*: Different methods are proposed to improve the coverage and support the communication networks with massive numbers of UEs, among which network densification and mm-Wave communications are considered. Network densification refers to the deployment of multiple RUs of different types in, e.g., metropolitan areas. Particularly, it is expected that in the future small nodes, such as relays, IAB nodes, repeaters, etc., may be deployed to assist the communications.

In this section, we introduce the concept of NCRs, as one possible low-complexity device to support for D-MIMO network densification. In simple words, NCR is a full-duplex amplify-and-forward repeater with beamforming capabilities at both transmit and receive side under network control. As illustrated in the Fig. 3, the NCR Mobile Termination (MT) is defined as a functional entity to communicate with a gNB via Control link (C-link) to enable the information exchanges, e.g., side-control information. The C-link is based on the NR Uu interface. The NCR-forwarding (NCR-Fwd) is defined as a functional entity to perform the amplify-and-forwarding of uplink/downlink (UL/DL) RF signal between the gNB and the UE via BH link and access link (see Fig. 3 for the illustration

of different links). The behavior of the NCR-Fwd is controlled according to the side control information received by the NCR-MT from the controlling gNB.

Fig. 3. Illustration of network-controlled repeater.

From a different perspective, RIS may be a possible technology for beyond 5G networks. It enables the control of the electromagnetic properties of the RF waves by performing an intelligent adaptation of the phase shift toward the desired direction. In general, intelligent surfaces are electromagnetically active artificial structures with beamforming capabilities that can be used to reshape the propagation environment such as to improve capacity, coverage, and energy efficiency. Similar to the NCR structure, RIS may also need a control link for configuration, but no specific FH/BH link and access link are designed with separate beamforming capabilities.

2) *Analog Fronthaul*: The choice of D-MIMO network architecture and its functional split depends on the bandwidth of the overall system. For mm-Wave and sub-THz frequency bands with very large bandwidths, conventional digital interfaces may not be suitable for FH links and analog FH connections can be utilized instead. Also, the RUs may not be able to handle digital processing for such high bandwidth signals and cannot remain small size enough for large-scale installation if low power consumption is desired. Thus, the use of wired or optical wireless analog FH links [18], [19] is a potential solution for high frequency and high bandwidth D-MIMO networks. To minimize both the power consumption and the size of the RUs, their processing is limited to basic components such as passive Optical Add-and-Drop Multiplexer (OADM), wideband Photo Detector (PD), and Directly Modulated Laser (DML), and further analog components for transmission and reception, see in Fig. 4. The use of wavelength division multiplexing allows multiple RUs to be connected to the same fiber cable. Furthermore, as D-MIMO requires synchronization of the FH links of the spatially distributed RUs to realize C-JT, a cost-efficient solution is to use analog FH in combination with centralized processing, e.g., precoding and channel estimation are performed in DU, where constraints are more relaxed and higher power consumption is acceptable.

B. Digital approaches

1) *Digital Beamforming*: Digital beamforming is a technique to improve the directivity and gain of the signals. The processing, i.e., precoding, is performed by a digital processor, which combines the signals to shape, steer the beams in

Fig. 4. A wide bandwidth D-MIMO network implementation using Analog-radio-over-fiber and wavelength-division multiplexing.

the desired directions, and create nulls if necessary, resulting in improved system performance, increased coverage, and enhanced resistance to interference and jamming. In D-MIMO, multiple antenna elements are placed at different geographical locations to form a distributed antenna array, where precoding allows for dynamic reconfiguration of the beam direction, enabling multiple beams to be formed and directed towards multiple UEs simultaneously, thus providing increased system capacity and improved user experience.

In case of limited bandwidth, e.g., 10-100 MHz, digital processing is feasible in the RU having a dedicated analog-to-digital converter and can be carried out locally. Digital processing at high-frequency bands, e.g., mm-Wave and sub-THz, will be power-consuming and increases the chip cost and size of the processing unit. Since small RUs are essential in terms of deployment aspects, we may need to move the digital processing from RU to DU, which would need high-capacity FH links. Nonetheless, centralized processing supported by advanced coordination can obtain better performance.

III. D-MIMO SYSTEM ENABLERS

A. Channel Estimation for D-MIMO in Dynamic Scenarios

Channel estimation is one of the foundations of wireless communication methods for both centralized and distributed MIMO. Since the distributed antennas typically serve a large number of users, the RUs prefer to deliver as many pilots as possible to users to avoid pilot contamination. However, the pilot assignment overhead becomes a significant issue with the increased number of pilots. Partial connections between RU and UE are significantly weakened in a D-MIMO network due to the rapid decay between RU and UE with increasing distance and the influence of blockers. Thus, when we consider only the strong connections between RUs and UEs, we can represent the connectivity of the D-MIMO network using a partially connected bipartite graph, which is the D-MIMO network's topological structure. In D-MIMO networks, the connection between the UE and the RU is affected by a number of factors, such as the mobility of users and the changing propagation environment, and these factors can affect the system's topological structure, see Fig. 5. In this case,

Fig. 5. D-MIMO topological structures modification under dynamic scenario.

Fig. 6. DL sum-rate versus pilot dimension under the dynamic scenario.

previously proposed pilot assignment methods [1]–[4] must be recalculated and then estimated for the new channels.

To avoid recalculation in dynamic scenarios, we propose a highly robust Maximum Distance Separable (MDS)-based method for handling the pilot assignment problem. As a linear code that exceeds the singleton limit, all k columns of the generator matrix of an MDS code $\mathcal{C}(n, k)$ are linearly independent. This character ensures that the rank of any sub-matrix formed of k vectors from the generator matrix is full rank. Due to this feature, it is possible to design pilot assignment vectors using MDS codes. Each RU receives a combination signal from all UEs, with only the most dominant T pilot signals being evaluated. Thus, if $T \leq k$, the dominant k channels can be estimated ideally by using the MDS-based pilot assignment strategy.

To compare the performance of our proposed MDS-based method, Fig. 6 depicts the sum rate versus the pilot dimension T_p for former pilot assignment algorithms under dynamic conditions. In this figure, we compare our proposed concept with sequential Maximum Weighted Induced Matching (sMWIM) [3], Information-Based K -Means (IBKM) [2], and

a semi-random pilot assignment approach [1]. To generate the MDS code, we adopt the Reed-Solomon code, which is the most often used method [20]. Observing from this figure, the MDS-based method has the highest sum rate when the pilot dimension is $T_p = 8$, while the semi-random method has the best performance when the pilot dimension is small, i.e., $T_p = 2, 4$. Unlike the performance under static conditions, the robustness of other methods that depend on the connection structure presents a worse performance.

B. Layer-1 Mobility and Non-coherent Joint Transmission

In addition to macro-diversity overcoming the path-loss and removing the blocking effect, D-MIMO enables robust access links that support Layer-1 (L1) mobility, where channel aging becomes visible due to time-varying propagation environment, and high carrier frequency operation. The precoder and serving RU subset update, i.e., L1 mobility, have been analyzed in a DL indoor scenario over UE-centric clusters for 16 UEs operating at 28 GHz [21]. The impact of update periodicities, e.g., 100 ms and 1 s, are examined for both multi-user C-JT and NC-JT (case 2b in 3GPP [14]). The precoder must be concurrently updated when the serving RU subset has been updated, whereas RU subsets may not require as frequent updates as the precoder. The reason is that the key factor for RU-UE association is slow fading, which is mainly affected by the path loss, where propagation model is set as in [22].

Fig. 7. Average SE of C-JT and NC-JT for 16 UEs at 28 GHz and different serving RU subset sizes and update periodicities (100ms & 1s).

Fig. 7 compares the D-MIMO performance for C-JT & NC-JT, and different serving subset update periodicities. Each RU transmission power is limited to 13 dBm, and each RU and UE is equipped with a single antenna. In addition, perfect channel estimation and lossless, high-capacity FH is assumed. For the best performance, one needs both phase coherency and frequent serving subset update, i.e., larger subsets provide higher SE values with C-JT if the subset updates frequently

Fig. 8. Mesh based IAB problem formulation.

during UE mobility, whereas more RUs degrades the performance without coherent operation. In general, performance degradation has been observed for longer update periodicity, but one can argue that its effect on C-JT is substantial, i.e., frequent subset updating is much more important for C-JT, however, it is not critical for NC-JT. If longer serving subset update periodicity is adopted, C-JT cannot outperform NC-JT.

C. Mesh based IAB with Multi-connectivity Access

Wireless links at high carrier frequencies (upper mm-Wave) result in lower link budgets, thus, lower reliability. Blockage can become a major issue at higher frequencies. Potential techniques to address these two issues are:

- 1) Reducing the range of links - for example by moving RUs closer to UEs.
- 2) Introducing link redundancy in the network by using multi-connectivity of nodes and mesh architectures.

In Fig. 8 a generalized architecture, using D-MIMO in the access links (UE-RU) and a mesh network architecture in the FH (RU-RU) is illustrated. All links are assumed to be wireless. Only a subset of the RUs is connected to the DU with base-band functionality, as shown in Fig. 8. The problem to be addressed is to associate UEs with RUs and to optimize a route between RUs such that link-loss in the mesh can be tolerated and potential inter-link interference is minimized.

It can be shown that for a given network scenario (deployment, user-density, antenna-patterns, etc.), increasing the number of RUs yields more reliable access links (higher probability that a UE has multiple reliable links to RUs). When the number of RUs is increased beyond a certain limit the access no longer improves significantly, but instead the mesh will become interference limited if not sufficiently many RUs in the mesh are connected to the DU.

D. Constrained IAB Deployment Optimization

IAB networks, may not be deployed in some areas and locations due to deployment constraints. Such constraints may be due to several reasons, e.g., due to the regulatory restrictions preventing such activities in protected areas, limitations due to the federal laws relating to forest protection, listed buildings, and air traffic safety. Furthermore, the deployment constraints can also be due to the network planning requirements, e.g., limit the interference, thus may affect inter-node distance.

Fig. 9. Illustration of an IAB network with deployment constraints, a) geographical constraints on node placement and b) minimum required inter-node distance.

In Fig. 9, an illustration of such deployment constraints are depicted. Especially, due to the radio frequency properties, network planning for minimum inter-node distance is important in well-planned wide-area IAB networks, i.e., type of IAB-nodes where MT part of the IAB node looks like a normal gNB, in terms of, e.g., high transmit power, antenna gain. On the other hand, the local-area networks (i.e., with IAB nodes having MT transmit powers between those of UEs and gNB) may still face deployment constraints due to various reasons, e.g., regulatory restrictions, and forest protection.

Evaluating different algorithms for such constrained deployment optimization has thus become vital. One such approach is to propose heuristic algorithms, as the optimization problem can be NP-hard. In our study in [23], the effect of network planning on the service coverage of such networks is considered. Greedy-based algorithms are proposed to optimize IAB placement with minimum inter-IAB node distance and geographical constraints, respectively. In there, the methods are based on the rejection-sampling method where multiple possible solutions are checked such that, satisfying the constraints, the service coverage is maximized. As the results show, the service coverage can be considerably improved via proper planning. Thereby, developing novel, efficient algorithms to address such constrained optimization problems is important.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we provided an overview of D-MIMO systems for 6G networks, discussed its potential offerings and deployment options, and introduced a categorization of the sub-components: transport medium, signaling, processing, and transmission aspects. The impact of robust channel estimation has been shown in dynamic scenarios. Moreover, the performance of NC-JT has been explored when L1 mobility is incorporated in the D-MIMO network operating at mm-Wave, showing the impact of clustering updates for NC-JT and C-JT. Mesh-based IAB with multi-connectivity access, and con-

strained IAB deployment optimization have been discussed. As a next step, efficient and reliable transmission schemes and algorithms need to be developed under practical constraints, and AI-assisted radio air interface design can improve end-to-end performance and enhance resource utilization.

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